

Contribution to the knowledge of entomofauna of a Belgian Famenne village. XIV. Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)

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Abstract – Ichneumon wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) of the subfamily Campopleginae are treated. A hundred species are included, forty-two of which are reported for the first time from Belgium: *Campoletis crassicornis* (Tschek, 1871), *Campoletis punctata* (Bridgman, 1886), *Campoletis thomsoni* (Roman, 1915), *Campoletis varians* (Thomson, 1887), *Campoplex formosanae* Horstmann, 2012, *Campoplex tibialis* (Szépligeti, 1916), *Casinaria mesozosta* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Casinaria pyreneator* Aubert, 1960, *Cymodusa australis* (Smits van Burgst, 1913), *Cymodusa declinator* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Diadegma crassiset*a (Thomson, 1887), *Diadegma flexum* Horstmann, 1973, *Diadegma kyffhusanae* Horstmann, 1973, *Diadegma maculatum* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Diadegma micrurum* (Thomson, 1887), *Diadegma neomajale* Horstmann, 1969, *Diadegma rufigaster* Horstmann, 1973, *Dusona insignita* (Förster, 1868), *Dusona libertatis* (Teunissen, 1947), *Dusona limnobia* (Thomson, 1887), *Dusona minor* (Provancher, 1879), *Dusona pulchripes* (Holmgren, 1872), *Echthronomas facialis* (Thomson, 1887), *Enytus parvicanda* (Thomson, 1887), *Eriborus terebrans* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Hyposoter aglyphus* Galsworthy et Shaw, 2023, *Hyposoter castaneus* Galsworthy et Shaw, 2023, *Hyposoter inquinatus* (Holmgren, 1860), *Hyposoter placidus* (Desvignes, 1856), *Hyposoter virginalis* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *Nemeritis caudatula* Thomson, 1887, *Nemeritis lativentris* Thomson, 1887, *Nemeritis specularis* Horstmann, 1975, *Nepiesta mandibularis* (Holmgren, 1860), *Olesicampe proterva* (Brischke, 1880), *Olesicampe radiella* (Thomson, 1885), *Olesicampe retusa* (Thomson, 1887), *Phobocampe lymantriae* Gupta, 1983, *Phobocampe tempestiva* (Holmgren, 1860), *Porizon albistriae* (Horstmann, 1987), *Rhimphoctona lucida* (Clément, 1924), and *Sinophorus nitidus* (Brischke, 1880). The presence of *Diadegma ruficeps* (Holmgren, 1860) in Belgium is confirmed.

Key words – species records, distribution, new occurrences, Western Palearctic Region

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INTRODUCTION

In this fourteenth contribution to the study of the entomofauna of the village of Somal (Commune of Somme-Leuze, Province of Namur, Belgium), we treat the ichneumon wasp subfamily Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). The village of Somal (UTM Square 31UFR68) is located in the Belgian natural region of Famenne. The description of the habitats encountered was detailed in a previous paper (LIBERT 2011).

Before this study, several species of Campopleginae captured by the first author in the village of Somal were published: *Dusona bicoloripes* (Ashmead, 1906), *Gonotypus melanostoma* (Thomson, 1887), and *Hyposoter rivulator* Galsworthy et Shaw, 2023 (VERHEYDE *et al.* 2021, GALSORTHY *et al.* 2023).

The material examined was partly singled or swept by the first author between 2004 and 2024, and partly captured using a Malaise trap installed in a meadow at forest edge in 2019 (KURINA & LIBERT 2020). Specimens were mounted on a card or pinned. Part of the specimens was identified by the late Klaus Horstmann (*Dusona* Cameron, 1901), Anthony Galsworthy (*Hyposoter* Förster, 1869, partly) and Dmitry Kasparyan (*Bathyplectes* Förster, 1869, *Nemeritis* Holmgren, 1860, *Rhimphoctona* Förster, 1869, *Scirtetes* Hartig, 1838, partly), others by the second author who also revised most of the previous identifications. Majority of the specimens is preserved in the personal collection of the first author (Libert Collection, abbreviated as LC); the remainder are deposited in the Hymenoptera Collection of the Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary (abbreviated as HNHM); the actual depository is provided for each specimen. Taxa are listed in alphabetical order. Among species new for Belgium, voucher specimens of those are depicted which have not already been represented by photographs in previous literature or in scientific quality websites. Photos were taken with a Nikon-D7200 camera, applied with Nikon AF-S Micro Nikkor 105mm objective and DCR-150 Raynox Macro Conversion lens managed by Helicon Remote, stacked by Helicon Focus.

RESULTS

Subfamily: Campopleginae Förster, 1869
Bathyplectes exiguus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.IV.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by MARÉCHAL (1926). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic and Nearctic Regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Bathyplectes immolator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1–6.IV.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Bathyplectes quinqueangularis (Ratzeburg, 1852)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 5.V.2009, one female, on *Salix capraea* L. (Salicaceae), meadow (Kasparyan det., LC); ibidem, 2.V.2011, one male, swept on a hedge, forest firebreak (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 23–30.IV.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 4–15.V.2019, one male, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 23–30.V.2019, two females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., one female in HNHM; one female in LC); ibidem, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region and only known from Mongolia in the Eastern Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2023).

Campoletis annulata (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 7–17.IV.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 16–27.V.2019, one male, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by GHESQUIÈRE (1947). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis cognata (Tschek, 1871)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 27.VIII.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 4–15.V.2019, one male, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis crassicornis (Tschek, 1871)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1.VI.2022, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis latrator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 11–24.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis punctata (Bridgman, 1886)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.V.2008, one female, swept on *Quercus robur* L. (Fagaceae), garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Bulgaria, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Norway, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis thomsoni (Roman, 1915)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 6.VII.2008, one female, on *Daucus carota* L. (Apiaceae), garden (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 28.VI.2010, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 31.VII.2010, one female, on *Quercus robur*, forest edge, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 16.VIII.2018, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 23–30.IV.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 1–3.V.2019, one male, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 11–24.VI.2019, two females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 28.VI–16.VII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 17.VII–15.VIII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis varians (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 17.VII–15.VIII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoletis zonata (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 14.IX–18.X.2019, two females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); *ibidem*, 10.VI.2023, one female, on *Daucus carota* flowers, dry wasteland, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by BORMANS (1885). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2017).

Campoplex difformis (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.VI.2017, one female, on *Rubus* sp. (Rosaceae), oak-hornbeam grove (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Campoplex formosanae Horstmann, 2012

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 2.VI.2015, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Germany, Hungary, and the United Kingdom (HORSTMANN 2012, SHAW *et al.* 2016).

Campoplex melanostictus Gravenhorst, 1829

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 7.V.2018, one female, flying around a damp embankment, sunken path, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Campoplex tibialis (Szépligeti, 1916)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 23.VI.2010, one female, swept in a flowery wasteland (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 12.VII–15.VIII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 14.IX–18.X.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 5.VII.2023, one female, on *Daucus carota* flowers, dry wasteland, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from France, Germany, Hungary, Norway, and Poland (YU *et al.* 2016).

Casinaria ischnogaster Thomson, 1887

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 4–15.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Libert rev., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018).

Casinaria mesozosta (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 17.VII–15.VIII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Libert rev., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it is widely distributed (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Casinaria moesta (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 30.V.2021, one male, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by LECLERCQ (1942). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2022).

Casinaria morionella Holmgren, 1860

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.VII.2005, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium* L. (Apiaceae), edge meadow-hedge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018).

Casinaria petiolaris (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 25.VI–16.VII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Libert rev., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018).

Casinaria pyreneator Aubert, 1960

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 5.VIII.2009, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, forest path, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, France, Germany, Poland, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018).

Cymodusa australis (Smits van Burgst, 1913)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 14.IX–18.X.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022).

Cymodusa declinator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.VI.2023, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, edge of forest path (Vas det., HNHM); *ibidem*, 12.IX.2023, one female, swept on a hedge, on the edge of a meadow (Vas det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022).

Diadegma claripenne (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 13.IV.2007, one female, swept in a meadow with *Cardamine pratensis* L. (Brassicaceae) (Vas det., LC); *ibidem*, 4.V.2010, one female, on budding shrubs, damp forest path (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma crassiseta (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 26.VII.2006, one female, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma erucator (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 15.VI.2011, one female, swept on a hedge, in the sun, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma fenestrata (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1.IX.2006, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, meadow (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Oriental and Palaearctic Regions, and it has been introduced to Australia and the USA (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma flexum Horstmann, 1973
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Bulgaria, Germany, Poland, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma grisescens (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.V.2023, one female, swept on a hedge, edge of a meadow (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 10.VI.2023, one female, swept on a hedge, edge of a meadow (Vas det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS & TOSQUINET (1890). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma hygrobium (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 25.VI–16.VII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 12.VIII.2023, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma kyffhusanae Horstmann, 1973

(Fig. 2)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Germany, Italy, and Poland (HORSTMANN 1973, AUBERT 1983, KAZMIERCZAK 2004). More recently, it was also discovered in Iran (BAHREMAND *et al.* 2022).

Diadegma maculatum (Gravenhorst, 1829)

(Fig. 3)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 11–24.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma micrurum (Thomson, 1887)
(Fig. 4)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 12.IX.2023, one female, on *Petroselinum crispum* (Mill.) Fuss. (Apiaceae) flowers, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from France, Germany, Italy, Norway, Poland, and Sweden (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2022).

Diadegma neomajale Horstmann, 1969

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 14.VI.2015, one female, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Germany, Norway, Poland, Sweden, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia and Iran (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023, VAS *et al.* 2024).

Diadegma ruficeps (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.VII.2020, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – Presence in Belgium confirmed: the species was previously listed, however with a “?” mark in Belgian checklist (THIRION 2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma rufigaster Horstmann, 1973
(Fig. 5)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, and Poland (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Iran (VAS *et al.* 2024).

Dusona admontina (Speiser, 1908)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1.VIII.2009, one female, trapped in a tent, garden (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – The presence of the species in Belgium is based on our specimen, reported by HORSTMANN (2011). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona aemula (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 28.V–10.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona angustata (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 22.VII.2010, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 30.V.2015, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 4.VI.2015, two females, on *Quercus* sp., forest path, in the sun (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 23.VIII.2015, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona angustifrons (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 7.VII.2006, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 29.V.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 1.VI.2012, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2021).

Dusona annexa (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.VI.2007, one female, on low vegetation, clearcutting, oak-hornbeam grove (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 25.VII.2010, one female, foraging *Petroselinum crispum*, garden (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 2.VII.2010, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region, and is also known from the Nearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona aversa (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 13.VIII.2010, one male, flying around a hedge, garden (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region, and is also known from the Nearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona baueri Hinz, 1973

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 27.IV.2006, one female, on low branches of *Corylus avellana* L. (Betulaceae), hedge (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – The presence of the species in Belgium is based on our specimen, reported by HORSTMANN (2011). A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Belgium, Finland, Germany, Poland, and Sweden (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona bicoloripes (Ashmead, 1906)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 12.VI.2010, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, meadow (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 30.IV.2012, one female, swept on shrubs budding, clear-cutting, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 4.V.2012, two females, swept at ground level, in herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 25.VIII.2015, one female, swept on a hedge, garden (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 3.IX.2015, one female, n herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 7.V.2018, one female, on shrubs, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 1.VI.2020, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – The presence of the species in Belgium is based on our specimen, reported by HORSTMANN (2011), contrary to cited elsewhere (VERHEYDE *et al.* 2021). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona blanda (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 2.V.2011, one male, flying around a hedge, garden (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 15.V.2010, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, damp forest path (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 16.V.2020, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona circumcinctus (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1.VII.2006, one male, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 25.VII.2004, one male, resting on a pile of logs, meadow (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Dusona circumspectans (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 4–15.V.2019, one male, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Dusona confusa (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 24.VIII.2006, one female, on *Daucus carota*, roadside (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2021).

Dusona cultrator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 14.IV.2007, one female, on low vegetation, forest path (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 30.V.2015, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona erythrogaster (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.VI.2012, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 15.VIII.2011, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 2.VI.2013, one male, one female, on *Quercus* sp., forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 2.VI.2013, one male, on *Quercus* sp., forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 30.V.2020, one female, flying, edge meadow-forest, in the sun (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Dusona flagellator (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16.VIII–13.IX.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona genalis (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by VERHEYDE *et al.* (2021). A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, and Switzerland (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona infesta (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 21.IX.2014, one female, flying around *Quercus* sp., forest path (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by VERHEYDE *et al.* (2021). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Dusona insignita (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 2.V.2011, one female, on a hedge, garden (Horstmann det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona libertatis (Teunissen, 1947)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 9.VII.2013, one female, swept on *Anthriscus sylvestris*, roadside (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022). Recently, it was also discovered in Iran (FEIZI *et al.* 2024).

Dusona limnobia (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 8.V.2010, one male, on leaf of *Acer pseudoplatanus* L. (Sapindaceae), in the sun (Horstmann det., LC); *ibidem*, 31.V.2014, one female, on vegetation on the edge of a large pond, near the Eau de Somme River (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Iran (FEIZI *et al.* 2024).

Dusona mercator (Fabricius, 1793)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 12.VII.2010, one male, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); *ibidem*, 6.V.2011, one female, flying around *Quercus* sp., forest edge (Horstmann det., LC); *ibidem*, 4.V.2015, one female, on *Anthriscus sylvestris* (L.) Hoff. (Apiaceae), forest path in the sun (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by BORMANS (1885). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019, VERHEYDE 2021). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2021).

Dusona minor (Provancher, 1879)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Holarctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, Germany, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Sweden, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, VERHEYDE 2021).

Dusona opaca (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.VIII.2023, one female, on *Daucus carota* flowers, dry wasteland, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 1–3.V.2019, one male, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by HORSTMANN (2011). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022).

Dusona polita (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 8.V.2005, one male, on *Carpinus betulus* L. (Betulaceae), forest path, Bois de Failon (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 28.V–10.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 25.V.2020, one female, on *Malus sylvestris* (L.) Mill. (Rosaceae), garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Dusona pulchripes (Holmgren, 1872)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.VII.2023, one female, swept in herbaceous vegetation, forest hedge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Ireland, Norway, Slovakia, Sweden, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona stenogaster (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 7.V.2018, two females, swept in a meadow with *Ranunculus acris* L. (Ranunculaceae) (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 18–22.IV.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 16–27.V.2019, two females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona stragifex (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 28.V.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 29.V.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 22.VII.2010, one female, flying around a hedge, garden (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 23.VIII.2015, one female, flying around a hedge, garden (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 16–27.V.2019, two females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 28.V–10.VI.2019, three females, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 11–24.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 13.V.2022, one female, trapped in a green house, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona subimpressa (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 4.V.2012, one male, swept on budding shrubs, in the sun, Bois de Failon (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 29.V.2011, one male, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 20.VII.2014, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 7.V.2018, one male, on shrubs, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 5–15.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, MEIER *et al.* 2022). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2021).

Dusona tenuis (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.V.2011, one male, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 4.VIII.2022, one female, trapped in a greenhouse, garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dusona terebrator (Förster, 1868)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.V.2011, one male, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 12.VI.2015, one female, swept on *Heracleum sphondylium*, forest edge (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 23.VIII.2015, one male, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by LECLERCQ (1942). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019).

Echthronomas facialis (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 7.VII.2006, one male, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 29.V.2011, one female, on a window, inside a house (Horstmann det., LC); ibidem, 3.VII.2014, one male, on *Salix* sp., banks of Eau de Somme (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 22.VIII.2015, one female, on a window, inside a house (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Italy, and Poland (YU *et al.* 2016).

Enytus parvicanda (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 25.VI–16.VII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2025).

Eriborus braccatus (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 10.IX.2024, one male, on *Daucus carota*, xeric wasteland, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Eriborus terebrans (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.VII.2015, one female, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. Almost worldwide and widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Gonotypus melanostoma (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 25.VI–16.VII.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by VERHEYDE *et al.* (2021). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VERHEYDE *et al.* 2021).

Hyposoter aglyphus Galsworthy et Shaw, 2023

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 5.VIII.2009, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, forest path, Bois de Failon (Galsworthy det., LC); ibidem, 11–24.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. This recently described species has been known only from France, and the United Kingdom (GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023).

Hyposoter castaneus Galsworthy et Shaw, 2023

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., LC); ibidem, 28.V–10.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. This recently described species has been known only from Germany, and the United Kingdom (GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023).

Hyposoter inquinatus (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 16.VIII–13.IX.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., LC); ibidem, 11.VII.2023, one female, swept on herbaceous vegetation, forest edge (Libert and Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 9.VIII.2023, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, edge of forest path (Libert and Vas det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023).

Hyposoter placidus (Desvignes, 1856)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 14.VII.2008, one male, swept on herbaceous vegetation, flowery meadow (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by SHAW *et al.* (2016). A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Andorra, Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Poland, Spain, Switzerland, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, KLOPFSTEIN *et al.* 2019, SIELEZNIOW & KOSTRO-AMBROZIAK 2019, GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023).

Hyposoter virginalis (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.VII.2010, one male, foraging *Pastinaca sativa* L. (Apiaceae), vegetable garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023).

Leptocampoplex cremastoides (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 2.VII.2017, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, megaphorbia border (Galsworthy det., LC); ibidem, 5.VIII.2023, one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, forest path (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). Holarctic distribution. It is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016).

Meloboris collector (Thunberg, 1822)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Vas rev., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by MAC LEOD (1894). It is distributed in the Afrotropical, Oceanic and Holarctic Regions. It is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Armenia, Jordan, Kosovo, and Serbia (VAS 2019a).

Nemeritis caudatula Thomson, 1887

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 6.V.2006, one male, swept in a meadow with *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik. (Brassicaceae) (Vas det., HNHM); ibidem, 15.IX.2024, one male, on flowers of *Hedera helix* L. (Araliaceae), garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Nemeritis lativentris Thomson, 1887

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 28.V–10.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., LC); ibidem, 15.VI.2023, one female, on *Daucus carota* flowers, dry wasteland, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. Holarctic distribution. In Europe, it has been known from France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Sweden, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2020).

Nemeritis specularis Horstmann, 1975

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 25.VI.2020, one male, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. Oriental and Palearctic distribution. In Europe, it has been known only from Austria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, and Poland (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2020).

Nepiesta mandibularis (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.IV.2007, one female, swept in a meadow with *Cardamine pratensis* (Kasparyan det., LC); ibidem, 18.VI.2006,

one female, on *Heracleum sphondylium*, forest edge (Kasparyan det., LC); ibidem, 25.IV.2008, one male, on low vegetation at the foot of a hedge, meadow (Kasparyan det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2019a).

Olesicampe flavicornis (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.VI.2010, one female, on *Quercus* sp, meadow edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region, and was reported from India; in Europe, it has been known from Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, and Sweden (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Olesicampe nigricoxa (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1–3.V.2019, one male, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). A Western Palaearctic species. It has been known only from Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, and Sweden (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Norway (RIEDEL 2022).

Olesicampe proterva (Brischke, 1880)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 18.V.2008, one female, swept on *Quercus robur*, garden (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Olesicampe radiella (Thomson, 1885)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.VI.2009, one male, swept on herbaceous vegetation, edge of the forest, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Olesicampe retusa (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1–3.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM); 4–15.V.2019, one female, ibidem (Vas det., LC); 16–27.V.2019, one female, ibidem (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL & JAPOSHVILI 2021).

Phobocampe bicingulata (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 16–27.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Vas rev., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). A Holarctic species. It is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016).

Phobocampe lymantriae Gupta, 1983
(Fig. 6)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 26.VI.2009, one female, on a window, inside a house (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Austria, Czech Republic, France, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and former Yugoslavia (YU *et al.* 2016, VERHEYDE *et al.* 2023). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Phobocampe tempestiva (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 19.IV.2010, one male, on *Chrysosplenium alternifolium* L. (Saxifragaceae), near Eau de Somme (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known from Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, and the United Kingdom (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2019b). Recently, it was also discovered in Georgia (RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Figs 1–6. Voucher specimens of selected species, all females, 1 = *Diadegma flexum* Horstmann, 1973, 2 = *Diadegma kyffhusanae* Horstmann, 1973, 3 = *Diadegma maculatum* (Gravenhorst, 1829), 4 = *Diadegma micrurum* (Thomson, 1887), 5 = *Diadegma rufigaster* Horstmann, 1973, 6 = *Phobocampe lymantriae* Gupta, 1983 (photos by Zoltán Vas)

Porizon albistriae (Horstmann, 1987)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.VI.2013, one female, swept on *Anthriscus sylvestris*, roadside (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. A Western Palaearctic species. In Europe, it has been known only from Germany, and Poland (YU *et al.* 2016).

Rhimphoctona lucida (Clément, 1924)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 29.V.2022, one female, on softwood logs (*Picea?*, *Larix?*), Les Aloux (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Rhimphoctona megacephalus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.V.2006, one female, on a wood pile, garden (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 10.VI.2006, one female, resting on a wood pile, garden (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 16.VI.2006, one male, flying around a wood pile, oak-hornbeam grove (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 14.IV.2007, one male, on budding *Carpinus betulus*, Bois de Failon (Libert det., LC); *ibidem*, 10.VI.2007, one male, on a window, inside a house (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 2.IV.2009, one female, on a window, inside a house, from a log of *Quercus* sp. (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 22.IV.2010, one male, on a window, inside a house, from a log (?) (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 23.IV.2011, one male, on a window, inside a house, from a log (?) (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 25.V.2012, one female, on a window, inside a house (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 12.V.2015, one female, on herbaceous vegetation, forest path (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 4.VI.2015, two females, resting on a felled trunk, forest path, in the sun (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 25.V.2016, one female, laying on a *Quercus* sp. wooden stake, meadow (Galsworthy det., LC); *ibidem*, 17.II.2022, one male, on a window, inside a house, from a log (?) (Libert det., LC); *ibidem*, 5.V.2022, one male, from *Prunus spinosa* L. (Rosaceae) log, inside a house (Libert det., LC); *ibidem*, 13.V.2022, one male, flying around logs, garden (Libert det., LC); *ibidem*, 27.V.2022, one male, on a wood pile, garden (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by THIRION (2005). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Romania (VAS 2019b).

Rhimphoctona obscuripes (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 13.V.2022, two female, flying around softwood logs (*Picea?*, *Larix?*), Les Aloux (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 30.V.2022, one female, on softwood logs (*Picea?*, *Larix?*), Les Aloux (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by HORSTMANN (1980). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Rhimphoctona rufocoxalis (Clément, 1924)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 13.V.2022, one female, flying around softwood logs (*Picea?*, *Larix?*), Les Aloux (Libert det., LC); ibidem, 30.V.2022, two females, on softwood logs (*Picea?*, *Larix?*), Les Aloux (Libert det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by LIBERT & VERHEYDE (2021). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2017) and Romania (VAS 2019b).

Rhimphoctona xoridiformis (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 11.VI.2006, one female, on *Rubus* sp., oak-hornbeam grove (Kasparyan det., LC); ibidem, 22.V.2008, one male, on herbaceous vegetation, meadow (Kasparyan det., LC).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by LIBERT & VERHEYDE (2021). It is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic Region (YU *et al.* 2016). Recently, it was also discovered in Ukraine (VARGA 2017).

Scirtetes robustus (Woldstedt, 1874)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 1.V.2010, one female, on *Corylus avellana*, hedge in a meadow (Kasparyan det., LC); ibidem, 1–3.V.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by MARÉCHAL (1927). A Palaearctic species. It is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016).

Sinophorus nitidus (Brischke, 1880)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.VIII.2023, one female, swept on a hedge, on the edge of a meadow (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First record from Belgium. It is distributed in the Oriental and Holarctic Regions; in Europe, it has been known from France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, and Sweden (YU *et al.* 2016, Di Giovanni & Riedel 2017).

Sinophorus turionum (Ratzeburg, 1844)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 20.VI.2009, one female, foraging *Rubus* sp., forest edge, Bois de Failon (Vas det., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS (1903). It is distributed in the Oriental and Palaearctic Regions; it is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016).

Tranosemella praerogator (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined – Belgium: Somal, 28.V–10.VI.2019, one female, Malaise trap in a meadow at forest edge (Galsworthy det., Vas rev., HNHM).

Remarks – First mentioned from Belgium by JACOBS & TOSQUINET (1890). It is distributed in the Oriental and Palaearctic Regions; it is widely distributed in Europe (YU *et al.* 2016).

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